

Genetic Evaluation of Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) Genotypes for Breeding Potential

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Abstract: Choosing superior parents with complementary trait values for hybridization and selecting variants with desired product profiles to release as a new cultivar are important breeding activities to progress genetic improvement in crops. This study assessed the genetic potential of 30 parental lines of tomato genotypes. This selection was performed focusing on 15 traits using variation and genetic parameters namely, phenotypic variance (PV) and genotypic variance (GV), genotypic coefficients of variation (GCV), phenotypic coefficients of variation (PCV), broad-sense heritability (hBS) and genetic advance. Descriptive statistics and analysis of variance revealed a wide range of variability for all the traits. Estimated hBS for all the measured traits ranged from 46.20% to 99.98% indicating that all the traits were highly inheritable. Genetic variances were ranged from low to high for most of the quantitative and qualitative traits, indicating complex genetic architecture.

Keywords: Tomato, Genetic improvement, Variability, Descriptive statistics, Heritability

I. Introduction

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.), belonging to the Solanaceae family with a chromosome number of $2n=24$, holds a significant position as one of the most crucial vegetable crops globally. India ranks second in the world tomato production (FAOSTAT, 2022). In India, tomatoes are cultivated across approximately 863.98 thousand hectares of land, resulting in a total production of 20.62 million metric tons and an average productivity of 23.87 tons per hectare. Among the states, Madhya Pradesh stands out as the leading producer with an area of 121 thousand hectares and a production of 2.76 million tons. In terms of productivity, Uttar Pradesh ranks highest with 39.99 tons per hectare (Indiastat, 2023). Tamil Nadu, on the other hand, produced 1.20 million tons on 33,860 hectares of land, achieving a commendable productivity rate of 35.42 tons per hectare. It is considered a vital protective food due to its exceptional nutritional value, offering an abundance of well-balanced nutrition, including vitamins, dietary fiber, minerals, ascorbic acid and other essential nutrients (Chaudhary *et al.*, 2018). According to Chikkeri *et al.* (2023), the full potential of tomatoes remains untapped because there is insufficient data available on the suitable varieties for particular agro-climatic conditions. The ability of tomato to thrive in tropical conditions has led to various adaptive and morphological changes. However, the intentional introduction of desirable traits and heightened selection pressure within the tomato population has led to a reduction in its genetic diversity (Bhattarai *et al.*, 2018). Without genetic variation, crop breeding endeavors do not yield any significant improvements. Biometric measures such as the GCV (Genotypic Coefficient of Variation), PCV (Phenotypic Coefficient of Variation), heritability, and genetic advance are valuable tools used to assess genetic variability and adaptability (Aditya *et al.*, 2011). The primary objective of this study was to explore the inherent variation among 30 tomato breeding lines and identify

promising candidates with significant genetic diversity. These selected lines would then be incorporated into crop improvement programs, using advanced multi-disciplinary analysis as the basis for the selection process.

II. Materials and Methods

The experiment was executed at the experimental site of Department of Vegetable Science, Horticultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore during 2021-2022. The site is located at 11°N latitude, 77°E Longitude and at an altitude of 426.26m above mean sea level. Thirty genotypes containing twenty four breeding lines from repository of Department of Vegetable Science, TNAU, Coimbatore and Six germplasm from World vegetable Centre, Taiwan and 2 released varieties from IHR Bengaluru (Arka Rakshak) and TNAU, Coimbatore (Tomato Hybrid CO 3) were used in the study (table). The genotypes were arranged in Randomized Block Design (RBD) with three replications. The seeds were sown in trays on 13th June, 2021 and were transplanted on raised beds in the field at a spacing of 75 × 60cm. All the regular agronomic practices were followed and the fruits were harvested in regular intervals. Total of fifteen biometrical observations were recorded following standard procedure. The traits were plant height (PH) in cm, number of primary branches, days to first flowering, Days to 50% flowering, number of flowers per inflorescence, number of locules, pericarp thickness (cm), number of fruits per cluster, number of clusters per plant, single fruit weight, number of fruits per plant, lycopene content (mg/100g), ascorbic acid content (mg/100g), total soluble solids (°Brix), percent disease incidence and yield per plant (g). The plants were inspected for Tomato Yellow Leaf Curl Virus incidence at 30, 45, 60, 75 and 90 days after transplanting. The study involved calculating phenotypic and genetic variance (PV and GV), along with genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation (GCV and PCV), using the formula provided by Falconer, 1983. Furthermore, the determination of broad sense heritability (hBS) and genetic advance (GA) followed the method elucidated in Burton, 1952.

III. Results and Discussion

A. Descriptive Statistics

A summary of the descriptive statistics, encompassing means and standard error, CV, minimum and maximum value for all the traits assessed in the research were presented in the Table 1. The summary of the descriptive statistics offers insights into the central tendencies and variations within each trait and also allowed to have a preliminary understanding of the trait distributions. It is found that the phenotypic variance value for the number of clusters per plant was higher than the genotypic variance, which indicated that the environment regulates the expression of the trait; the environmental impact is comparatively low for all other traits. This finding coincides with the findings of Aidoo *et al.*, 2014.

B. Genetic Variability Components

For every variable, the result of the genetic parameters, including the phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV), genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV), broad-sense heritability (hBS), and genetic advance as the percent of the mean (GAM), are presented in Table 2. The proposed index of 0–10% for low, 10–20% for moderate, and >20% for high variation was used to characterize the projected GCV and PCV values. Single fruit weight recorded the highest GCV (35.35 %) and PCV (35.43 %) while Days to first flowering recorded the lowest GCV (9.63 %) and PCV (9.96 %). Genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation was observed to be high for 10 traits, medium for four traits and low for one trait. Broad-sense heritability was ranged from 46.20% to 99.98% and it is found to be high for all the observed traits except number of clusters per plant which was found to be medium.

Table I. Descriptive statistics of measured traits

Traits	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Standard Error	Coefficient of Variation (CV %)
Plant Height(cm)	98.05	69.25	132.20	1.80	2.25
Number of Primary Branches	11.76	6.87	18.28	0.43	4.53
Days to First Flowering	33.93	25.00	40.00	0.69	2.52
Days to Fifty Percent Flowering	36.92	27.00	45.00	0.74	2.48
Pericarp Thickness (cm)	0.53	0.29	0.81	0.01	3.35
Number of Locules	3.93	2.00	6.00	0.00	0.00
Number of Flowers per Inflorescence	4.97	2.67	8.33	0.23	5.80
Number of Clusters Per Plant	30.27	11.17	69.07	0.47	4.83
Number of Flowers Per Cluster	4.03	2.00	7.40	0.11	3.36
Single Fruit Weight(gm)	67.38	26.64	120.16	1.27	2.31
Number of Fruit Per Plant,	48.74	22.12	99.63	1.63	4.10
Total Soluble Solids (°brix)	4.05	2.21	4.72	0.09	2.76
Lycopene Content (mg/100g)	5.66	3.99	8.28	0.07	2.04
Ascorbic Acid Content (mg/100g)	25.55	11.04	42.71	0.54	2.60
Yield Per Plant (gm)	2600.64	1139.60	3824.40	41.84	1.97

Table II. Analysis of statistical and genetic parameters of yield and its contributing traits across various tomato genotypes.

Traits	GV	PV	GCV(%)	PCV(%)	hBS(%)	GA	GAM(%)
Plant Height(cm)	277.22	282.08	16.99	17.14	98.28	34.00	34.71
Number of Primary Branches	8.05	8.33	24.13	24.56	96.60	5.75	48.87
Days to First Flowering	10.69	11.42	9.63	9.96	93.60	6.52	19.20
Days to Fifty Percent Flowering	14.59	15.43	10.34	10.64	94.57	7.65	20.73
Pericarp Thickness (cm)	0.01	0.01	21.77	22.01	97.84	0.24	44.37
Number of Locules	1.37	1.37	29.81	29.81	99.98	2.42	61.41
Number of Flowers per Inflorescence	1.87	1.96	27.57	28.17	95.77	2.76	55.58
Number of Clusters Per Plant	69.98	151.47	27.63	40.66	46.20	11.71	38.70
Number of Flowers Per Cluster	1.61	1.63	31.53	31.71	98.88	2.60	64.59
Single Fruit Weight(g)	567.57	569.99	35.35	35.43	99.57	48.97	72.68
Number of Fruit Per Plant,	217.75	221.74	30.27	30.55	98.20	30.12	61.80
Total Soluble Solids (°brix)	0.21	0.22	11.27	11.61	94.35	0.91	22.56
Lycopene Content (mg/100g)	1.26	1.28	19.87	20.04	98.32	2.30	40.59
Ascorbic Acid Content (mg/100g)	42.79	43.23	25.60	25.74	98.98	13.41	52.48
Yield Per Plant (g)	624572.01	627198.04	30.39	30.45	99.58	1624.60	62.47

GV = Genotypic variance, PV = Phenotypic variance, GCV = Genotypic coefficients of variation, PCV = Phenotypic coefficients of variation, hBS = broad-sense heritability, GA = Genetic advance at 5% selection intensity, GAM = Genetic advance as the percentage of the mean at 5% selection intensity

The GCV and PCV showed high values for the number of primary branches, pericarp thickness, number of locules, number of flowers per inflorescence, number of clusters per plant, number of fruits per cluster, single fruit weight, number of fruits per plant, ascorbic acid, and yield per plant, suggesting that these traits were under the influence of genetic control. Days to first flowering exhibited low GCV and PCV values, suggesting relatively limited genetic and phenotypic diversity for this specific trait. Moderate GCV and PCV were recorded for the traits plant height, days to 50% flowering, and TSS, and similar results were previously reported by Maurya *et al.* (2022) in tomato. It is also observed that a majority of the traits had closely estimated PCV and GCV values. These traits appeared to be less affected by environmental factors, indicating that selection based on these traits could be considered reliable (Premabati Devi *et al.*, 2016).

The strong GAM coupled with heritability was utilized to assess the significance of certain traits in the selection process. Medium GAM was possessed by days to first flowering and high GAM by all the other traits. All the traits were found to have crucial potential due to their minimal susceptibility to environmental influences, with the exception of DF, which showed moderate values. The occurrence of high heritability coupled with high genetic advance as a percent of mean for all the traits except DF implies preponderant additive gene action. In such situations, selection is likely to be highly effective. Hence, effective selection necessitates choosing higher values of GCV, PCV, hBS, and GA, indicating that the impact of additive genes is more consistent and reliable compared to environmental factors (Ritonga *et al.*, 2018 & Maurya *et al.*, 2022).

IV. Conclusion

In this study, 30 tomato parental lines were evaluated across 15 traits, indicating high heritability for all traits. Notably, traits such as the number of branches, pericarp thickness, and yield per plant displayed significant genetic control. These traits, characterized by high genetic advance percentages, are well-suited for selection in breeding programs, offering the potential for enhanced tomato varieties. These findings hold promise for improving tomato crops, benefiting both agricultural production and consumers through the development of superior tomato cultivars with desirable traits.

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